

Rise of Digital Education and E-Learning in India: an Assessment of Use of Technology for Equitable Education

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Abstract

The New Educational Policy (NEP) 2020 of India directed the country towards physical, emotional, and cognitive transformations of children and youth through education. With the advent of digital technologies, access to quality education has become increasingly democratized. However, with the rise of digital education and e-learning in India, the digital divide persists, disproportionately affecting marginalized sections of society. In this context, this research paper explores the transformative potential of digital education interventions in addressing the educational disparities experienced by children. The authors of the study analysed the scope and challenges of digital education in enhancing the learning outcomes and equitable education. The authors suggest that, if appropriately designed and implemented, digital education interventions can serve as a powerful tool for promoting equitable access to education. The study also recommended policy intervention for infrastructure development, digital literacy programs to maximize the positive impact of digital education among children and youth in India.

Keywords: Digital Education, E-Learning, Covid-19, Digital Divide, Equitable Education.

Introduction

The rapid ascent of digital education and e-learning in recent years especially after Covid-19 has unquestionably brought about a profound transformation in the educational landscape. This paradigm shift is based on the promise of expanding access to education and fostering a more inclusive and equitable learning environment. As technology continues to advance, the digital realm has become an indispensable tool for educators and learners alike, with a potential to break down traditional barriers that have hindered education for many.

However, as we delve deeper into this brave new world of digital education, it becomes increasingly apparent that there exist challenges and disparities that demand thorough scrutiny and thoughtful examination. The promises of digital education, such as broader accessibility and flexibility, are tempered by the complexities inherent in the fusion of technology and pedagogy. Issues surrounding the digital divide, varying levels of technological proficiency, and the potential for marginalized groups to be left behind in the digital revolution must be critically examined.

The Need of Digital Education and E-Learning

India has the largest youth population globally, the significance of this demographic cannot be overstated, as it represents a massive potential resource for the nation's future. To harness this potential effectively, it is imperative to provide these young individuals with the necessary skills and opportunities to not only secure a brighter future for themselves but also to contribute to the well-being of their families and the overall development of the country. The National Youth Policy 2021 is

a visionary document that lays out a ten-year roadmap for youth development. Its primary objective is to "unlock the potential of the youth to advance India" and catalyze progress in crucial areas such as education, employment, and entrepreneurship.

However, the landscape of education in India has transformed significantly since the first COVID-19 lockdown in March 2020. The pandemic expedited the adoption of digital media in education. While this shift offers promise, it also raises pressing concerns that demand attention. These include the persistent gender divide in access to digital resources and devices, the digital divide that separates rural and economically disadvantaged areas from the digital infrastructure required for effective learning, the concerning rates of school dropouts despite the digital transition, and the gradual decline in the role of government schools in providing quality education. Addressing these issues is pivotal to ensuring that the ambitious goals set forth in the National Youth Policy-2021, are achievable, enabling India's youth to truly become the driving force behind the country's progress and development.

Relevant Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

SDG 4, 5, and 10 intersect at a critical juncture, emphasizing the essential need for equitable access to education. SDG 4 champions the cause of quality education for all, recognizing that education is a fundamental human right and a cornerstone for individual and societal development. Meanwhile, SDG 5 places a strong emphasis on gender equality in education, acknowledging the persistent disparities that women and girls often face when pursuing education. These two goals collectively underscore the importance of creating inclusive educational systems that do not discriminate based on gender, ethnicity, or any other factors.

Furthermore, SDG 10 highlights the broader goal of reducing inequality within and among countries. This goal recognizes that unequal access to resources, opportunities, and services can undermine social and economic progress. Achieving equitable educational opportunities for all is a powerful means of reducing such inequalities. By ensuring that education is accessible to every segment of society, regardless of their background, SDG 10's objective becomes more attainable.

Digital Education for Teaching and Learning

Digital education, commonly known as e-learning, represents a revolutionary paradigm in the realm of teaching and learning. It is a dynamic approach that capitalizes on the capabilities of digital technologies to disseminate educational content, foster meaningful interactions, and nurture the growth of essential skills. This innovative concept encompasses a diverse spectrum of educational practices and tools, all unified by their shared reliance on the internet and digital devices. By harnessing these technological resources, digital education has the potential to substantially enrich the educational journey, making it more accessible, engaging, and adaptable to the needs of learners in the modern age.

Elements of Digital learning- Digital learning through online platforms offers a multitude of defining features that have transformed the way we acquire knowledge.

Multimedia Content: This feature refers to the use of various types of media, such as videos, animations, podcasts, and interactive simulations, to present educational materials.

Flexibility and Accessibility: Online learning platforms provide flexibility in terms of when and where learners can access educational resources. This flexibility breaks down traditional constraints, allowing individuals to learn at their own pace and according to their schedules. **Interactivity and Collaboration:** Interactivity and collaboration are at the heart of effective online learning. They enable students to engage actively with the content and with each other. Discussion forums, group projects, and live webinars are just a few examples.

Data-Driven Insights: Online learning platforms often collect data on student performance and engagement. This data is then analyzed to provide insights into how well a student is progressing. Educators can use this information to offer personalized guidance, identify areas where a student may be struggling, and adapt teaching strategies accordingly. In essence, data-driven insights make the learning experience more tailored and effective.

As technology continues to advance, online learning platforms are likely to evolve further, providing even more innovative ways to support learning and skill development. Digital learning brings with it several notable benefits that have reshaped the educational landscape. One of the most significant advantages is its wider geographic reach, as it transcends geographical boundaries, allowing learners from diverse locations to access high-quality educational resources. This global reach promotes cultural exchange and fosters a more inclusive learning environment. Furthermore, digital learning offers flexible learning options, enabling individuals to tailor their education to their schedules and preferences. This adaptability is particularly beneficial for working professionals and those with other commitments. Additionally, it is often more affordable than traditional educational methods, reducing costs associated with commuting, physical materials, and sometimes even tuition fees. These cost-saving benefits make education more accessible and cost-effective for a broader spectrum of learners, democratizing the learning experience.

Use of technology for promotion of equitable education is no doubt can be a game changer. Lot many initiatives announced by government of India in direction of online and e-Education (PIB, GoI, 2023). In India at state level one of the latest initiative is from kerala , about Kerala's digital education initiatives (EdTech) the UNICEF India study stated that, "Kerala's KITE-led EdTech model, without relying on profit-driven vendors, is both scalable and adaptable, making it valuable for other regions, the report pointed out.... it as a model not only for other Indian states, but also for middle-income and developed countries" (Indian Express, PTI, 2024).

National Education Policy (NEP-2020)

The National Education Policy of 2020, often referred to as NEP-2020, places a significant emphasis on harnessing technology to revolutionize education in India. This forward-looking policy recognizes the transformative potential of technology in the realm of learning. NEP-2020 advocates for the integration of digital resources and online education platforms, thereby making education more accessible and equitable for all. By embracing these technological tools, it envisions a future where students, regardless of their geographical location or socio-economic background, can benefit from a high-quality education. NEP-2020 is not only about fostering academic excellence but also about bridging the existing gaps in access and educational standards, ushering in a new era of tech-driven education that promises to make learning more inclusive and effective. This approach aligns with the changing dynamics of the modern world and the need to prepare students for the challenges of the digital age. But challenges faced by digital education in India are multifaceted and critical to address for the country's educational advancement. A paramount need in this context is ensuring universal internet access.

Digital Divide, Gaps and Challenges in India

The rapid expansion of digital platforms presents both opportunities and challenges in today's interconnected world. While the proliferation of these platforms is undeniable, there are significant gaps and challenges that demand attention. Inclusivity is a critical concern that often takes a backseat in this technological surge. The digital divide continues to persist, leading to disparities in access, particularly in terms of gender. The gender gap in digital participation remains a significant issue, with women frequently underrepresented in the digital landscape. Additionally, disparities in mobile ownership further exacerbate the divide, as not everyone has equal access to the tools and resources needed to fully engage in the digital realm. Addressing these challenges and ensuring inclusivity in the expansion of digital platforms is essential for creating a more equitable and interconnected world. It requires a concerted effort to bridge these gaps and make technology accessible to all, regardless of gender or socio-economic status.

Internet penetration rates in India have shown some fluctuations in recent years. In 2019, it reached a peak of 50%, which was a promising sign for the digital education landscape. However, in 2020, it experienced a setback, dropping to 45%. While there was a gradual increase to 47% in 2021 and 48% in 2022, these numbers appear relatively small considering India's vast population of 1.4 billion people. Bridging the digital divide and expanding internet infrastructure to remote and underserved

areas is an essential task that demands government intervention to facilitate information accessibility and ensure that digital education can truly reach every corner of the country. (Statista 2023)

Equipping individuals from economically disadvantaged backgrounds with the necessary devices and technology is imperative to ensure education isn't out of reach for them. The following table depicts the key data figures from NFHS 5:-

Table 1: Literacy and digital access status of people in India

Key Indicators NFHS-5	Urban	Rural	Gap	Total	NFHS-4
Women who are literate (%)	83.0	65.9	~18%	71.5	NA
Men who are literate (%)	89.6	81.5	~9%	84.4	NA
Women with 10 or more years of schooling (%)	56.3	33.7	~23%	41.0	35.7
Men with 10 or more years of schooling (%)	62.1	43.7	~22%	50.2	47.1
Women who have ever used the internet (%)	51.8	24.6	~27%	33.3	NA
Men who have ever used the internet (%)	72.5	48.7	~25%	57.1	NA

Source : NFHS-5 (2019-21)

Digitalisation of Education and Privatisation

In the era of digitalisation of education and privatisation India needs to ensure equitable delivery of education to all. Safeguarding Indian education and avoiding privatization of the Indian education ecosystem is crucial to ensure equitable access for all in India. Public education, when adequately funded and regulated, promotes inclusivity and provides opportunities regardless of socio-economic background. As per the National Education Policy, 2020 (NEP) mandate India's education budget should increase as per need of the sector. Since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, the already dismal condition of the education system in India has been exacerbated, with schools remaining closed for about 20 months, leading to poor learning outcomes, especially among the poor and disadvantaged.

Privatization can lead to increased costs, creating educational disparities favoring those who can afford quality education. Unified District Information System for Education Report (2021-22), shows the decreasing share of Government schools. According to the report in 2020-21 total schools were 15 lakh (1509136 schools), which became 14 lakhs (1489115 schools). Out of which private were 3.34 lakh and government were 10.3 lakh. In the year 2021-22 the total Schools were 15 Lakh out of which private were 3.46 Lakh and the government were 10.2 lakh. A slight decrease in the share of government schools at national level is clearly visible.

Furthermore, the lower public expenditure on education in India, coupled with the availability of data on public expenditure from different ministries, further worsens the plight of the education sector.

India's education spending has lagged behind other middle-income countries, with most states allocating only 2.5% to 3.1% of state income to education. The 2021-22 Budget saw a concerning trend of reduced public spending on education by both the central and state governments, despite the ongoing education crisis. Furthermore, last year, the Education Ministry's budget allocation increased by a marginal 8 percent from Rs 1.12 lakh crore as opposed to 1.04 lakh crore in 2022-23. These challenges highlight the urgent need for improvement in the upcoming budget for coming years, particularly in the education sector.

UNESCO recommends public education spending levels of 4% to 6% of GDP and 15%-20% of public expenditure by 2030, yet India falls short, spending only 14.1% of its budget on education.

Comparatively, countries like Vietnam and Indonesia allocate a higher share of their budgets to education, despite having similar GDP levels, underscoring the need for increased investment in India's education sector. A strong public education system remains vital to address the vast educational needs of India's diverse population. It upholds the principles of equity and social justice, ensuring that every child, regardless of their economic status, has access to quality education. Balancing private and public sector involvement is essential to maintain this equitable approach to education in the country.

Budget allocation towards education should be the foremost priority of governments over other political issues. Investing in education is a fundamental pillar for the overall development and progress of a nation. It is through education that societies can break the cycle of poverty, improve their economic prospects, and foster a more informed citizenry. Prioritizing education in budget allocation demonstrates a commitment to building a better future for all citizens. Private educational systems should be effectively regulated to ensure quality and fairness in education. While private institutions can play a significant role in expanding educational opportunities, they must be held to standards that guarantee the delivery of quality education. Regulation can help prevent profiteering and maintain equitable access to education, making sure that the interests of students and society as a whole are protected.

Digital and Gender Divide

In developing countries like India, the digital divide is a pressing concern. According to a report by Patrika in July 2020, only 38% of the total population has access to the internet, leaving a significant 62% without access to the digital world. While India has made rapid strides in improving internet access, particularly through mobile internet use, which nearly doubled from 2018 to 2020, the disparity between men and women in terms of digital access remains striking. The National Family Health Survey-5 (NFHS-5) data, spanning from 2019 to 2021, provides a sobering insight. It reveals that, for the first time, the survey assessed internet use among both men and women. Shockingly, it was found that only one in three women in India (33%) have ever used the internet, while more than half (57%) of men have enjoyed digital connectivity. This significant gender gap in digital access highlights a critical issue that must be addressed to ensure equitable participation in the digital age, especially in a country as diverse and populous as India. (Source: NFHS-5 Factsheet).

The data on availability, use & ownership of computers suggests that of all youth, 9% have a computer and out of it 85% can use it. In all youth, 91% do not have a computer and out of it 34% can use it. Wherein the Smartphone category depicts that 89% of all youth have a smartphone at home 92% can use a smartphone and among those who can use a smartphone 31% have their own smartphone. In all males who can use a smartphone, 44% have their own smartphone. Among all females who can use a smartphone only 20% have their own smartphone (ASER-2023). In comparison to that, out of all males who can use a smartphone, 44% have their own smartphone. It shows a big gender difference in owning digital devices to leverage opportunities for going forward in education (ASER-2023).

In recent years, there has been a notable shift in women's engagement with mobile internet in low and middle-income countries, as per the GSMA's 2022 report. While there has been an encouraging rise in women's adoption of mobile internet, the pace of this progress has considerably decelerated. This trend reveals that the mobile internet gender gap, which had previously shown signs of narrowing, has now reached a standstill. Across these regions, women are currently 16 percent less likely than men to utilize mobile internet services, which equate to a staggering 264 million fewer women than men benefiting from this technology. The persistent challenge of reaching the 372 million women who are still without access to a mobile phone remains a critical issue that requires innovative solutions.

The GSMA-2022 report identifies several key barriers hindering women's access to mobile ownership and, consequently, mobile internet use. These barriers encompass affordability, digital literacy, and proficiency, safety concerns, and security issues. Addressing these obstacles is crucial in not only bridging the gender divide in mobile internet access but also in empowering women to harness the transformative potential of this technology. Recognizing the significance of these findings, it is

imperative for governments, organizations, and stakeholders to work collaboratively towards mitigating these barriers, ensuring equitable access, and fostering digital inclusion for all (Rani S. & Sharma K. 2020).

The impact of COVID-19 lockdowns on the developmental needs of children especially in rural India, was a matter of critical concern in 2020. As the pandemic swept across the globe, rural areas faced its own set of challenges. This case study delves into the repercussions of lockdowns on children's development in village settings with a particular emphasis on their emotional well-being, nutritional status, and access to education. Various study were carried out to capture ground realities of children belongs to diverse socioeconomic backgrounds. The findings were striking, revealing that lockdowns took a toll on the emotional health of children as they grappled with confinement and disrupted routines. Parents, forced to take on the role of educators, often struggled to provide suitable learning environments, leading to discomfort and adjustment issues for the children. The suspension of mid-day meals, a crucial source of nutrition for many, created a concerning nutrition gap, affecting the overall health of the children. Additionally, a glaring digital divide emerged, leaving many children with unequal access to online education, exacerbating disparities in educational opportunities. These findings underscore the complex and multifaceted challenges faced by rural India.

Needless to say online education system has its own challenges. Globally school and university students exposed to many challenges (Agustina D. et al., 2020). Indian population is divided due to socioeconomic status and diversity. In this context the role of government is crucial to bring parity in educational system. With more than 75 years of Independence the government of India continuously striving hard to achieve heights of socioeconomic progress. But due to various socioeconomic inequalities there are many challenges along with upcoming opportunities. In this scenario it is the duty of various stakeholders to learn lesson and reflect back on the systems which aimed at creating an inclusive society. In case of digital education during Covid -19 India experienced that, due to online educational systems different integrated programmes related to child development and growth were compromised. In this context if India would like to optimally use digital platforms for education few key points should be incorporated in creating inclusive policy.

Conclusion

It is essential to ensure the availability and accessibility of digital devices for all. In an increasingly digital world, access to technology is synonymous with access to education, information, and opportunities. Governments, communities, and organizations must work together to bridge the digital divide, making digital devices and the internet accessible to everyone, regardless of their socioeconomic status or geographic location. The right to education should be guaranteed by all public and private institutions, with a particular focus on marginalized sections of society. Education is a fundamental human right, and its availability should not be dependent on one's background. Governments and private entities should take active steps to ensure that every individual, especially those from marginalized communities, has equal access to quality education, empowering them to break barriers and achieve their full potential. Special efforts should be made to reduce the gender gap in education, promoting intersectional collaboration among all stakeholders. Globally gender disparities in education is an important matter of concern and various policies are designed and implemented to reduce it at national and international level. Further, to rectify this, it's imperative to implement time bound target based policies and programs to empower girls and women to pursue education and careers. Additionally, fostering collaboration between governments, NGOs, and communities is essential to creating an inclusive environment where gender equality in education is a reality, not just a goal.

References:

- ASER Centre. (2023). ASER Report 2023. Retrieved from chrome-extension://https://asercentre.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/ASER-2023-Main-Findings_Final-22.2.24-1.pdf
- Agustina D. et al., (2020), Challenges of Having Online Learning Activities: University Students' Perspectives. Retrieved from https://ineltal.um.ac.id/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/Dwi-

- Agustina-Sarlita-D.-Matra-and-Sayyidatul-Karimah-Challenges-of-Having-Online-Learning-Activities_University-Students%E2%80%99-Perspectives.pdf
- GSMA. (2022). Connected Women: The Mobile Gap Report. Retrieved from <https://www.gsma.com/r/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/The-Mobile-Gender-Gap-Report-2022.pdf>
 - <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1946419>
 - Lok Sabha Secretariat Report on <Budget for the Education Sector in India> (No. 21/RN/). Retrieved from https://loksabhadocs.nic.in/Refinput/New_Reference_Notes/English/BUDGET.pdf
 - National Education Policy (NEP). (2020). Retrieved from https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf
 - National Youth Policy (NYP). (2021). Retrieved from <https://static.pib.gov.in/WriteReadData/specificdocs/documents/2022/may/doc20225553401.pdf>
 - PIB, (2023), Several landmark initiatives taken up under NEP 2020 for the transformation of Education Sector Posted On: 07 AUG 2023 4:25PM by PIB Delhi. Retrieved from
 - Rani S., & Maske S.,(2022), Covid-19 Lockdown and Critical Perspectives on Online Education, Recent Researches in Social Sciences & Humanities, Issue 5 (Special Issue) Vol. 09 Jan.-Feb.-Mar. 2022, ISSN 2348-3318.
 - Rani, S., & Sharma, K. K. (2020). Gender and Pandemic. Journal of Exclusion Studies, 10, 135-149.
 - Unified District Information System for Education Plus (UDISE+). (2021-22). Retrieved from https://dashboard.udiseplus.gov.in/assets/images/pdf/UDISE+2020_21_Booklet.pdf
 - National Guidelines and Implementation Framework on Equitable and Inclusive Education (NGIFEIE), Retrieved from https://dsel.education.gov.in/sites/default/files/update/NGIFEIE_dosel.pdf
 - PTI (2024), Kerala's digital education model a global exemplar, says UNICEF Study
 - <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/kerala-digital-education-model-unicef-study-9437322/>